

An Assessment of Ministry Of Lands, Survey and Town Planning As an Agency for Government Revenue Generation in Jos Metropolis.

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ Ali, Andesikuteb Yakubu, ⁽¹⁾ Vivan, Ezra Lekwot, ⁽²⁾ Danjuma, Andembutop Kwesaba, ⁽¹⁾ Sohotden, Christopher Daniel And ⁽³⁾ Mudi, Anayib

⁽¹⁾ Dept of Geography and Planning University Of Jos, Nigeria

⁽²⁾ Department Of Geography Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

⁽³⁾ Federal College of Forestry, Jos

ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to assess the revenue generation activities of Plateau State Ministry of Lands, Survey and Town Planning, Jos, it utilized and reviewed 2008-2013 budgets of Plateau State Government. The results show that Ministry of Lands, Survey and Town Planning is among the top three (3) key ministries with great capacity to generate revenue for the state government after the Plateau State Internal Revenue Service. The research has also revealed that ongoing reforms in the ministry are capable of putting it in position to overcome the bottlenecks that had persistently crippled the revenue generation capacity of the ministry in the years that past. It recommends among other things that delays in the implementation of the reforms which were thought to be responsible for the dip in revenues in some years should be eliminated to make the ministry achieve her objectives and become the most profitable in Plateau state.

Keywords: Revenue Generation, Land Resources, Town Planning, Land survey, Budgets

INTRODUCTION:

Land is the foundation of all forms of human activities. From it we obtain food, the shelter and clothing we need and the space we work (Dale and Mclaughlin, 1990). Binns (1990) sees land as man's most valuable resources and means of livelihood, a habitat whose wide use is crucial for the economic, social and environmental advancement which leads to human survival.

Land according to (Thompson, 2006) means different thing to different people, Geographers see land as physical place (space) which results from geological and geomorphological processes. Economists see it as a factor to be combined with labour and capital to achieve economic production and development. Others see and define land based on its usefulness and significance to their lives and activities. It is very crucial due to its ability to house water resources, plants and annuals, soil, air, and mineral resources which are raw materials for any form of production.

The ministry of lands, survey and town planning is established to issue certificate of occupancy to deserving citizens and is also saddled with the responsibility of implementing appropriate laws, land administration, allocation, town planning, and land surveys on behalf of government (PLAGIS Handbook, Undated). A lot of reforms carried out in the ministry by the Plateau State Government have resulted to the design of Greater Jos master plan, the creation of Plateau Geographical information system (PLAGIS) and the upward review of rates and fees on land title acquisition, registration and

ground rent payments. These reforms have equally slowed down and lengthened the process of obtaining land titles, a problem that PLAGIS was created to solve.

Most urban environments are developed and expanding in response to phenomenal economic development, population growth and government interventions (Wapwera, 2013). This equally leads to conversion of land from one form of use to the other leading to sprawling if the planning authorities fail to be on top of their activities (Ndabula, et al. 2014 and Danjuma, A.K. et al 2014). This should create an avenue to earning of incomes into government treasuries through collections like change of purpose clause fees, layout approval fees, recertification, contravention fees, building plan approval, survey fees, processing fees registration of documents, among others, individuals and legal practitioners who either engage in land sales or perfect legal mortgage documents on behalf of government and Bank are not left out in these benefits.

All aspects of land management deals with the process of planning and implementing policies of putting land into proper usage to avoid waste. Such decision as land allocation, development, formulation and implementation of land use policies maximizes returns to both government and individual land users.

Reforms on land are all deliberate policy changes that are geared towards prudent management and utilization of land resources to the benefits of all. Several major and slight reforms have been variously carried out at local, state and federal levels in Nigeria to

regulate the access and use of land for effective utilization in agriculture, construction, water resources management and industrialization which are centres of human activities, land once well managed brings enormous revenues to government and individual stakeholders right from the time of acquisition process to its utilization as the original owner receives either rent or reward for lease or outright sales, the agent earns commission.

AIM:

The paper is aimed at assessing the ministry of lands, survey and town planning as an agency of government revenue generation in Jos metropolis.

METHOD AND PROCEDURES:

This study used secondary data sources, the information obtained from the state budget of 2008-2013 to compare the revenue generated by the various key ministries and board of internal revenue services and the ministry of lands, survey and town planning for onward discussions. Also, personal observations of the authors complimented the gaps that were noticed in the budgets.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION :

The various fees charged by the ministry of lands, and survey in Jos are survey fees, contravention fees, registration and search of documents, consent fee, ground rents layout approval fees, building plan approval, recertification fees, site inspection fee and charge of purpose clause fees as seen in table 1. In the year 2012, Plateau State government approved an estimated amount of N1.990bn, from these collection and proposed N497.575million in 2013 having collected just N89,630020.21 in 2012. These fees in the year 2013 earned revenue to state coffers amounting to N131,402 million as against the targeted amount of N497,575m.

Table 1: Revenue generated from three major fees charge by Ministry of Lands, Survey and Town Planning (MLSTP) Jos.

Years	Reg. & search fee	Survey fee	Consent fee	Total
2009	38,828,781.91	75,175.00	650,350.00	39,554,306
2010	22,678,750	153,081	292,550	23,124,381
2011	19,601,668	1,121,590	1,550,556	22,273,814
2012	40,526,348.63	3,546,749	1,019,429.59	45,092,527
2013	22,677,221	12,979,790	3,070,400	38,727,411
Total	144,312,770	17,876,385	6,583,285.57	168,772,439

Source: Adapted from various Plateau States Budgets

The state Government through the ministry has witnessed an increase in income of over N42 million. Among these fees, registration and search of documents are the most profitable in 2010 fiscal year, this exercise budget in the income of N22.678m and in 2011, the sun of N19.60m was also realized and in 2013, the ministry was able to generate up to 131.402 million in actual revenue as against N1bn budgeted.

Table 2, on the other hand shows the various charges by state ministry of land and survey these ranges between N1000 – N1,000,000 depending on the activities to be carried out and the purpose of which the land will be put to. All these rates were recently reviewed upwards by the government to boost revenue base of the ministry.

Table 2: Summary of major Reviewed rates charged by Ministry of Lands, Survey and Town Planning, (MLSTP), Jos.

S/N	Category	Amount (N)	Remarks
1	Varied	25,000 – 73,000 (PFRO)	Residential/Comm. & Industry
2	Commercial x varied merge	25,000 – 1,000,000	Residential/Comm. & Industry
3	Varied	1000 – 75,000	Building plan approval
4	Varied	2000 – 10,000	Layout approval
5	Varied	5000 – 500,000	Change of purpose clause to residential
6	Varied	1200 – 5000	Intelligent fee inspection fee
7	Varied	12,000 – 90,000	Survey fees
8	Varied	5000 – 15,000	Registration of document
9	Varied	1,000 – 15000	Replacement of cost titles
10	Varied	10,000	Recertification
11	Varied	5000 – 15,000	Infrastructure levy
12	Varied	15,000 – 75,000	Contravention
13	Varied	1,000 – 15,000	Printing of maps / documents
14	Varied	5000 – 3% Consideration	Alienation of C& R of C
15	Varied	5,000 – 10,000	Others fees

Source: PLAGISHandbook

The revenue generated by the ministry of lands, survey and town planning as x – rayed in Table 3 shows that from 2008-2013, there was an astronomical increase in the sums of money accrued with only 2010 showing a decrease in the revenue generated of N32,308,353.34 out of the 2.4 billion budgeted. However, the year 2013 showed that N131, 402,601.24 was generated out of the N1billion budgeted. This indicates that the bottlenecks that had plagued the ministry before now are changing and with these changes the future is really bright and the ministry will stand shoulder high amongst ministry and agencies generating revenue for the state and its entire citizenry.

Table 3: Total Year on year revenue Generated by Ministry of Lands, Survey and Town Planning (MLSTP), Jos

Year	Revenue	Budget
2008	59,759,773.08	1.059bn
2009	-	-
2010	32,308,353.34	2.4bn
2011	48,235,423	2.4bn
2012	89,630,020.21	4.1bn
2013	131,402,601.24	1bn

Source: State budget 2008-2013

Table 4 put up the performance of some key ministry regarding revenue generation for the state from 2008-2013. In comparison with the revenue generated by ministry of lands survey and town planning in the same years (2008-2013), it is evident that only plateau state internal revenue service generated revenues that are higher than the MLSTP on yearly basis from (2008-2013), other ministries like Agriculture and Education had a slight edge over ministry of lands and survey on two and three occasions.

Table 4: Total year on year revenues generated by Board of Internal Revenue and Some key Ministries in Jos.

Years	Ministry	Budget	Revenue
2008	Agriculture	746,514,554	21,140,000
	Education	102,987,392	72,105,000
	Works	6050,000	8,178,230
	Water Res.	6500,000	4,534,171.24
	Board of Internal Revenue (BIR)	3261,500000	2,235,131934.04
2010	Agriculture	555,600.,000	6,003,480
	Education	172,500,000	60,268,637.70
	Works	11,870,000	4,501,575
	Water Res.	15,600,000	7,444,174.25
	Board of Internal Revenue (BIR)	5,600,000,0001	2,104,519,877.91
2011	Agriculture	1,032,605,000	785,230,000
	Education	190,200,000	185,248,410
	Works	12,270,000	2,607,875
	Water Res.	15,000,000	6,095,070
	Board of Internal Revenue (BIR)	5,712,000,000	2,628,460,371.97
2012	Agriculture	64,280,000	2,787,280
	Education	200,400,000	112,445,728
	Works	33,900,000	4,953,800
	Water Res.	12,000,000	2,0101,000
	Board of Internal Revenue (BIR)	6,605,000,000	4,784,819,323.26
2013	Agriculture	51,380,000	2,819,765
	Education	196,100,000	80,861,590
	Works	3,900,000	875,000
	Water Res.	14,000,000	11,948,783.23
	Board of Internal Revenue (BIR)	9,200,000,000	5,022,144,915

Source: State Budget

Cumulatively, over the period of five years (2008-2013) the ministry of lands survey and town planning became number three revenue generating government agency with the cumulative revenue generation of N361, 336,171 to education and Plateau state Internal Revenue Service with N510, 366 and 1.67 trillion respectively.

Before 2008, precisely during 2003-2007 the rates charged by the ministry of lands, survey and town planning concerning land were low and affordable, even at that people cut corners to achieved whatever they want, but the reforms that came up in 2008 saw all the charging rate reviewed upward and the usual business of the people were given way to due processes involved in land business. This also led to payments of all rates through commercial banks and this blocked the chances of diverting these revenues in the past. It is on this premise that the state has experienced a surge in revenue generation in the ministry of lands, survey and town planning.

CONCLUSION :

Land is everything to man as it as basic as air and water and support plants growth, surface and underground water which are used by man in all and activities and in addition support residential, commercial, industrial and agricultural uses. Land reforms, therefore, are necessary to harness all benefits and revenues to government, private companies and individuals.

In Plateau state obstacles to land related revenue generation are as follows:

- Inability of government to issue titled documents to those who purchase same.
- Missing files at ministry of lands stalls revenue generation activities
- Unwillingness on the part of land owners to obtain and register titles appropriately.
- Lands occupied by natives don't have title and do not earn revenues to government except for families who either rent out or used for farming purposes.
- Large parcel of land occupied by government don't pay ground rent as it wasn't purchased but compensated for.

RECOMMENDATIONS :

- i. Government should grant titles to deserving citizens without any form of delay and unnecessary bureaucracy at an affordable cost.
- ii. Computerization of the activities of ministry of lands, survey and town planning through the use of geographic information system would save time, bring down cost and bring higher returns to all stakeholders.
- iii. Legal framework that would spell out clearly the functions of all the MDA, private sector businesses, families and individuals as it relates to land transactions would go a long way in boosting the revenues of the state.
- iv. All native lands should be registered and the process of their reassignment regulated, registered and charged appropriately.

REFERENCES

Binns, B.O. as cited in Dale, P.F. and M.C. Laughlin, J.D. (1990). Land Info Mgt. An Intro with special reference to cadastral problems in Third World Countries, Oxford Science Publication, Oxford Newyork, Toronto, Delhi.

Dale, P.F. and Mclaughlin, J.D. (1990). As above

Ndabula, C. Jidauna, G.G., Averik, P.D., Oyatayo, T.K. Abaje, I.B. and Ali, A.Y. (2014). Characterization of Sprawling in Kaduna metropolitan Area. American Journal of Environmental Protection pp 131-137 No. 3 No. 3 www.sciencepublishinggroup.com/j/ajep accessed 20th Nov. 2014 12:15pm.

Danjuma, A.K., Ali, A.Y., Lagan, A.N. Jeb, D.N. and Karma, I.M. (2014). Determination of Change Matrix among the Land use/Land cover Types in Jalingo metropolis, Nigeria. International. *Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, vol. 8 No. 1 September 2014 pp 213-224 www.ijias.ISSN.Journal.org accessed 20th October, 11:30pm.